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Optimized management of reactive power reserves of transmission grid-connected photovoltaic plants driven by an IoT solution

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a methodology for the analysis and simulation of the effect of operating large photovoltaic (PV) plants, in coordination, as static synchronous compensators (STATCOM). The goal is to improve voltage profiles at different load nodes and reduce power losses in transmission lines. The proposed approach takes into account the varying reactive power capacity in PV inverters, which depends on weather conditions.

To implement the proposed method, proper Internet of Things (IoT) hardware and software solutions are required. In this context, the grid status and weather data need to be transmitted continuously, via wireless communication technology, to an edge computer. Based on the transmitted data, and using the system mathematical model, an optimization algorithm is then responsible for finding out the optimal reactive power setpoint for each plant in real time.

The proposed method is implemented and tested successfully using MATLAB platform with the MATPOWER IEEE 30-bus test grid model. When only five 20 MW PV plants are connected to different locations in the grid with a penetration rate lower than 25 percent, the simulation shows the effectiveness of the optimal coordination of PV plants to deal with the effect on the transmission grid of instantaneous operation of multiple loads. In this context, a daily load profile of heat pumps, operating in winter scenario in multiple households, is approved. An improvement up to 68 percent in the global voltage profiles in the load buses for one-day scenario is achieved. Furthermore, total accumulated active and reactive power losses are reduced by 24.1 percent.

1. Introduction

Solar energy is the most widely available source of renewable and sustainable energy and can play a leading role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions. One of the established means to transfer this energy and transform it into electricity is photovoltaic (PV) technology. Although PV technology is expensive, it has received strong support through various incentive programs [1] and, as a result, is becoming increasingly popular for connecting to the grid, both on large and small scales, to sustain the power balance. Additional technical benefits have been discovered recently when connecting large PV plants to the transmission networks, some of which are dealt with in the present paper. The approach consists of exploiting PV plants, not only as active power generators, but also as reactive power support according to the plant operational point; thereby, the plant can be operated as FACTS devices

(Flexible AC Transmission System).

Transmission and distribution networks experience I^2R heating losses due to the flow of current I through the resistance R of the lines. For example, Fig. 1 shows a comparative diagram for transmission power loss curves between Germany and Algeria; power losses in Germany are 4–6 percent of the total power delivered, whereas in Algeria they reached 20 percent in more than one case. Line losses are a function of voltages at different buses in a transmission or distribution network. One of the objectives of optimal power flow studies is to determine the voltage setpoints at different generator buses for an optimal power flow by minimizing the losses subject to system operating constraints [2].

As Fig. 2 shows, the PV power plant remains completely idle during nighttime; in this case, the entire reactive capacity of its inverters is unused. However, during daytime, the PV plant generates active power for the grid, either by using the whole inverter capacity (at rated power generation) or partial inverter capacity (during early mornings and late

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Nomenclature		MQTT	Message queuing telemetry transport
AC	Alternative current	OPC UA	Open-platform communications united architecture
API	Application Programming Interface	P	Active power
DC	Direct current	PC	Personal computer
DE	Differential evolution	PCC	Point of common coupling
FACTS	a Flexible alternating current transmission system	PLC	Programmable logic controller
GA	Genetic algorithms	PSO	Particle swarm optimization
IoT	Internet of Things	PV	Photovoltaic
IP	Internet protocol	PWM	Pulse-width modulation
LTE	Long-term evolution	Q	Reactive power
MAE	Mean absolute error	STATCOM	Static synchronous compensator
MPPT	Maximum power point tracking	SVC	Static var compensator
		TSO	Transmission system operator

Fig. 1. Yearly transmission losses evolution of Algeria and Germany power network systems [3].

Fig. 2. Reactive power capability simulation during one-day scenario for a 60 MW PV plant.

evenings or during cloudy periods). As a result, substantial capacity in inverters is left unexploited. Recently, some PV inverter manufacturers have taken this remaining capacity into consideration when designing internal control systems; the objective is to control the voltage level at the point of common coupling (PCC) by exchanging the remaining reactive power with the low voltage grid.

A new concept of using the PV plant inverter as a STATCOM during nighttime for voltage control was proposed in [4,5]. However, this concept was not demonstrated for daytime operation. In [6], PV plant inverters, while generating active power, have also been controlled to

provide reactive power compensation for loads connected at their terminals. Some earlier papers have presented sunny mode and night mode operation of three-phase PV grid-connected inverters [7,8]. In night mode, the PV plant inverters compensate the effect of the reactive power demanded by nonlinear loads. In sunny mode, they not only supply active power from the PV array to the grid or local loads, but also perform power quality control to improve the power factor and reduce the harmonic currents. However, none of those works have investigated the effect of operating the PV plant inverters for voltage control. Refs. [9,10] presented comprehensive test plans leading to the commissioning of a novel application of the PV plant inverters as STATCOM devices for voltage control and power factor correction, both during nighttime and daytime. Nevertheless, the studies are limited to the effect of a single PV plant on the voltage at PCC only. The range of effect of several PV plants on the global network, in terms of improving voltage and reducing losses in transmission lines, is still missing in the literature.

From the rated inverter capacity S (MVA), which is dimensioned according to the nominal power and number of connected PV modules at the DC link, the remaining reactive power Q (MVA) for PV-STATCOM operation is obtained as $Q = \sqrt{S^2 - P^2}$, where P (MW) is the active power produced by the solar farm. This shows clearly that there is a significant amount of unused capacity of PV inverters during large periods in the day (almost 30–40 percent), which can be used for PV-STATCOM operation; that is, if the active PV generation for a 60 MW power plant is the one plotted in red curve in Fig. 2, the blue curve represents the reactive power capability of the same plant for each

Fig. 3. 30-bus IEEE grid (buses surrounded by red circles are the ones selected to connect PV plants).

operation point.

The work presented in this paper investigated the effect of optimal exploitation of this varying reserve of reactive power of several PV plants on the global transmission grid. PV plants exchange, in coordination, reactive power with the network by adjusting their PCC voltages within an acceptable range. This coordination is performed by taking into account the reactive capability and location in the network of each plant, which requires high computational effort. Stochastic optimization tools are selected to deal with highly complex problems such as the

one mentioned earlier. This work proposes the use of particle swarm optimization (PSO) to find out the optimal reactive power reference for each PV plant; its performance will then be compared with the differential evolution (DE) optimization technique. The optimal reactive power management between PV plants and the grid aims to improve voltage profiles at different load buses and reduce transmission losses. Such “supervisory layer”, is to be integrated to the global missions of a transmission system operator (TSO). The real implementation requires specific hardware and software solutions, wireless communication protocols, appropriate IT infrastructure and enough cloud-based hardware resources, which makes it a fertile ground for Internet of Things (IoT) solutions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the system and the proposed method context; Section 3 gives more insights about the chosen optimization techniques and the adopted algorithms; Section 4 shows up the mathematical formulation of the optimization problem. Finally, Section 5 presents simulation and comments.

2. System and method description

The work presented in this article was performed on IEEE 30-bus 41-branch test grid. The voltage constraints in the lower and upper limits are 0.95p.u. and 1.05p.u., respectively. Buses 1, 2, 13, 22, 23, and 27 are connected with generators. Bus 1 is set as the swing bus, while the others are considered as P-V buses. The remaining buses of this system are P-Q buses (Fig. 3). As mentioned previously, this work proposes a new management strategy of large connected PV plants at different sites. It aims to benefit from the available reactive reserve in PV inverters as supplementary gain. The proposed method gives a new approach, in which the voltage profiles in load buses and the transmission losses in different lines are targeted. The voltage at a load bus is depending on active and reactive power flowing through this bus. Usually, weak buses that are relatively sensible to voltage collapse are sustained using FACTS devices like STATCOM and static var compensators (SVC) [11–13].

The proposed method consists of using the already existing PV plants to improve the grid exploitation without the need to install additional costly FACTS devices. This may have two main advantages: sustaining the installed generators by injecting more active power into the network and enhancing the operational performance of the transmission grid. This is possible during night, morning, and evening times when the insolation level is idle or not vertically projected over PV modules. The

Fig. 4. PWM three-phase inverter control diagram.

Fig. 5. IoT architecture solution for the proposed method.

total or partial cloudy periods can also make a significant active power generation drop. In both cases, PV plants run lower than their rated powers, which preserves sufficient MVar capacity. According to the localization in the network of each plant, and to its operational point, optimal reactive power sharing between different plants is possible. Therefore, optimal voltage level for each plant is to be found. Different PCC voltages will initiate optimal power flows in branches in the grid. When a cost function is well formulated, this power flow will decrease the power losses in the total lines and improve the voltage profiles globally in the load buses relatively to the location of each one in the

network. PSO and DE are selected, separately, to solve this optimization problem.

The selection of appropriate locations to connect PV power plant is based on identifying the weakest buses. Efficient methods are proposed in the literature to find out which buses are more sensitive to heavy loads in the network [14–16]. The identification of the weakest buses is an important task for the analysis of power system stability, but it has been excluded from this study since a simple simulation of an ordinary scenario can give a sufficient idea about which buses are more sensible for power demand. In 30-bus IEEE grid, the buses 6, 8, 11, 19, and 26

Fig. 6. Simplified optimization diagram.

Fig. 7. Simplified transmission line model.

were selected.

2.1. DC/AC converters control

The PWM control technique is widely used for inverters control due its simplicity and effectiveness [17]. For PV grid-connected applications, the control scheme aims to keep the DC link voltage constant, regardless of the operational point of the inverter. Thereby, the inverter is kept connected to the grid, even at nighttime when there is no active power to produce. If a MPPT algorithm adjusts the DC voltage reference permanently, this technique will ensure the feeding of the maximum available PV power to the grid. DC voltage regulation is usually accomplished using a PI (proportional integral) controller, in which the output is the angle phase φ of the PWM reference voltage (Fig. 4). If φ is shifted forward compared to the grid voltage at PCC, the inverter feeds active power to the grid and vice versa.

AC voltage at the inverter PCC is also adjustable by means of the reactive power exchange with the low voltage grid. This is accomplished using a PI controller/PWM, in which, the output is the voltage index U (Fig. 4). The inductance of the inverter filter, including the self-inductance of the connecting transformer, determines the amount of exchanged reactive power for a set PWM voltage reference magnitude. If U is higher than the PCC voltage, the inverter feeds reactive power, and vice versa.

2.2. Internet of Things

IoT is the technological basis for the implementation of the proposed management method. The grid status signals need to be transmitted in real-time, via internet protocol (IP)-based communication or 3G/long-term evolution (LTE) mobile networking, to an edge device via wireless communication technologies. The edge device can also host a web server to provide key data parameters to the end user using a web-based dashboard. Using a mathematical model of the transmission grid, solar irradiation data at each PV plant region, which is provided via application programming interface (API), and the grid status signals, the edge device can also be the stage for optimization algorithms in the context of edge computing. This optimization aims to find out the optimal reactive power setpoint to be applied for the next time interval for each plant. The real-time and historical data can be stored and provided locally in the edge device database. Optionally, long-term historical data can be

stored remotely in a cloud-based database for further analysis, so the data is accessible everywhere in the globe. Cloud computing is also suitable for more complex grid models.

As adopted in [18], the IoT architecture solution is composed of four layers: device layer, network layer, cloud management layer, and application layer.

- *Device layer* contains two sub-layers:
 - *Things layer*, where different types of sensors, smart meters, smart tags, and actuators, exist to sense environment and collect data.
 - Sometimes data can be collected better from a *gateway layer*, which contains microcontrollers, programmable logic controllers (PLCs), and databases that control how to connect to elements of things layer.
- The *network layer* sends the data securely from the device layer to the application layer. This can be accomplished via batch data or streaming data manners.
- The *cloud management layer* is responsible for data storage, data security, user applications backend, and user management. This layer can be also the stage for cloud computing when more hardware resources are needed for machine learning and optimization algorithms.
- The *application layer* provides services to end users with frontend functions including demand response management, dynamic pricing, or energy management.

Fig. 5 summarizes the different layers explained above while highlighting the different communication protocols suitable for such IoT architecture.

3. Optimization algorithms

As mentioned above, selecting the ideal value of the reactive power exchange for each PV plant in the transmission network, whatever the actual operational point is, is transformed to an optimization problem. Therefore, the chosen optimizer algorithm requires the following information as inputs:

- Actual power demand at each P-Q bus.
- Actual power generation at each P-V bus.
- Actual power production of each PV plant.

The chosen optimizer must also take into account:

- The location of each P-Q, P-V buses in the grid, and the location of each PV plant.
- The impedance of all grid lines.

In this paper, stochastic methods are adopted to solve the optimization problem explained previously. Stochastic optimization refers to a collection of methods for minimizing or maximizing an objective function when randomness is present. These methods play a significant role in the analysis, design, and operation of modern systems. Stochastic optimization algorithms have broad application to problems in statistics, science, engineering, and business. Simple concept, easy implementation, robustness to control parameters, and computational efficiency characterize such techniques when compared with deterministic algorithms and other heuristic optimization techniques [19]. Two stochastic methods – PSO and DE – were adopted in the present study. The advantages of PSO include less parameter tuning, easy constraints, and suitability for multi-objective optimization [20]. The advantages of DE include simplicity, efficiency, local searching property, and speediness [21].

A simplified diagram of the optimization process using both techniques is presented in Fig. 6, where the mentioned quantities $P_{g,i}$ and $Q_{g,i}$ are, respectively, the active and reactive power generation for each PV

plant. $V_{i,load}$ is the voltage value at the load bus i . Fig. 7 shows a simple model of a transmission line linking two buses i and j , and the corresponding electric quantities. For both techniques, the only required feedback signals are the voltage at different load buses; then a power flow problem is solved using MATPOWER platform in order to calculate the power flow in different branches and the voltage at different buses. The optimizer will then be able to calculate the voltage error in load buses, as well as the transmission losses using (5) and (8), respectively.

3.1. PSO optimization

PSO is a population-based stochastic optimization technique developed by Dr. Eberhart and Dr. Kennedy in 1995 [22], inspired by social behavior of bird flocking or fish schooling. PSO shares many similarities with evolutionary computation techniques such as genetic algorithms (GA). The system is initialized with a population of random values of solutions and searches for optima by updating generations. Unlike GA, however, PSO has no evolution operators such as crossover and mutation. In PSO, the potential solutions, called particles, fly through the problem space by following the current optimum particles. The following sections provide more detailed information.

PSO is initialized with a group of random particles (solutions) and then searches for optima by updating generations. In every iteration, each particle is updated by following two “best” values: the first one is the best solution (fitness) it has achieved so far; this value is called $pbest$. Another “best” value that is tracked by the particle swarm optimizer is the best value obtained so far by any particle in the population. This best value is a global best and called $gbest$.

After finding the two best values, the particle updates its velocity and positions with following Equations (a) and (b).

$$v(i+1) = v(i) + c_1 \cdot r_1 (pbest(i) - p(i)) + c_2 \cdot r_2 (gbest(i) - p(i)) \quad (1.a)$$

$$p(i+1) = p(i) + v(i+1) \quad (1.b)$$

Where i the number of iteration; $v(i)$ is the particle velocity; $p(i)$ is the current particle (solution); $pbest(i)$ and $gbest(i)$ are the best position for the particle and for the group respectively. r_1 is a random number between 0 and 1. c_1 and c_2 are learning factors. A pseudo-code for PSO algorithm is shown below:

```

Initialize parameters
Initialize population
while (stopping criterion not met){
  for (i = 1 to number of particles){
    if (the fitness of  $X_i^g$  is greater than the fitness of  $pbest(i)$ ){
       $Pbest(i) = X_i^g$ ;
    }
    if (the fitness of  $X_i$  is greater than  $gbest(i)$ ){
       $gbest(i) = X_i^g$ ;
    }
    update velocity vector;
    update particle position;
  }
  Next iteration;
}

```

3.2. DE optimization

Proposed by Storn and Price in 1995 [23], DE is a stochastic algorithm for maintaining a population with N_p individuals. Every individual in the population stands for a possible solution to the problem. One individual in the population is represented by vector $X_{i,g}$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, N_p$ and g referring to the index of the generation. A cycle in DE consists of three consecutive steps – mutation, crossover and selection – which are described as follows:

Mutation. Inspired by biological evolution, mutation is carried out in DE to facilitate random perturbations on the population. For each population member, a mutant vector is generated. In the basic version of DE, three different individuals are randomly selected in the population and then a scaled difference of any two of the three vectors is added to the third one to obtain the mutant vector. More precisely, this mutant vector is created according to (2).

$$V_{i,g} = X_{r1,g} + F \cdot (X_{r2,g} - X_{r3,g}) \quad (2)$$

Where $V_{i,g}$ represents the mutant vector, i stands for the index of the vector, g stands for the generation, $r1, r2, r3 \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_p\}$ are random integers and F is the scaling factor in the interval $[0, 2]$.

Crossover. This operation combines every individual in the actual population with the corresponding mutant vector created in the mutation stage. These new solutions created are called trial vectors and we use $T_{i,g}$ to represent the trial vector corresponding to individual i in generation g . Every parameter in the trial vector is decided in terms of (2).

$$T_{i,g}[j] = \begin{cases} V_{i,g}[j] & \text{if } rand[0,1] < CR \text{ or } j = j_{rand} \\ X_{i,g}[j] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where j stands for the index of every parameter in a vector, J_{rand} is an integer between 1 and N_p to ensure that at least one parameter from mutant vector will enter the trial vector and CR is the probability of recombination.

Selection. This operation compares a trial vector and its parent solution in the current population to decide the winner to survive into the next generation. Therefore, if the problem of interest is minimization, the individuals in the new generation are chosen using (3).

$$X_{i,g+1} = \begin{cases} T_{i,g} & \text{if } f(T_{i,g}) < f(X_{i,g}) \\ X_{i,g} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $T_{i,g}$ is the trial vector, $X_{i,g}$ is an individual in the population, $X_{i,g+1}$ is the individual in the next generation, $f(T_{i,g})$ represents the fitness value of the trial vector, and $f(X_{i,g})$ stands for the fitness value of the individual in the population.

The pseudo-code of DE algorithm is summarized below:

```

Initialize parameters
Initialize population
while (stopping criterion not met){
  for (i = 1 to population size){
    mutation;
    crossover;
    selection;
  }
}

```

4. Problem formulation

4.1. Improving voltage profile

This section represents a methodology for determining the optimal reactive power exchange for each PV plant in order to enhance the voltage level at load buses. As a test of a 24-hour scenario, 24 different operation points in terms of PV active power generation and active/reactive power demand are set. In this context, the general optimization problem can be solved by minimizing the cost function formulated in (5):

$$J = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{NB} (1 - V_i)^2}{NB} \quad (5)$$

Where V_i is the voltage at the bus i and NB is the number of load buses in the network.

The equality and inequality constraints to be satisfied while searching for optimal solutions can be formulated in (6) and (7), where N is the number of buses; P_{gi} and Q_{gi} are respectively the active and reactive power generations at i_{th} bus; δ_{ij} is the deference between voltage angles between i and j buses.

$$P_{gi} - P_{di} = |V_i| \sum_{j=1}^N |V_j| (G_{ij} \cos(\delta_{ij}) + B_{ij} \sin(\delta_{ij})) \quad (6.a)$$

Table 1
Ain El-Bell PV Plant Parameters.

Module	Power	250 W
	Open-circuit voltage	37.6 V
	MPP voltage	29.8 V
	Short-circuit current	8.92 A
	MPP current	8.39 A
	Module model	YL250P29b
	Plant	No. of modules in series per one string
No. of modules in parallel per one string		2
No. of strings per junction box		4/6/8
No. of junction boxes per parallel box		4
No. of parallel boxes per inverter		4
No. of inverters per 0.4KV/30KV transformer		2
No. of 0.4KV/30KV transformers connected to 30KV/60KV transformer		20
MPP DC voltage		600–800 V
Rated power		20 MW

Fig. 8. Proposed profile for both active and reactive power demands.

$$Q_{gi} - Q_{di} = |V_i| \sum_{j=1}^N |V_j| (G_{ij} \sin(\delta_{ij}) + B_{ij} \cos(\delta_{ij})) \quad (6.b)$$

$$P_{gi}^{\min} \leq P_{gi} \leq P_{gi}^{\max} \quad (7.a)$$

$$Q_{gi}^{\min} \leq Q_{gi} \leq Q_{gi}^{\max} \quad (7.b)$$

$$V_i^{\min} \leq V_i \leq V_i^{\max} \quad (7.c)$$

At each bus i , P_{gi}^{\min} and P_{gi}^{\max} are the minimum and maximum active power generation, respectively; Q_{gi}^{\min} and Q_{gi}^{\max} are the minimum and maximum reactive power generation, respectively; and V_i^{\min} and V_i^{\max} are the minimum and maximum allowed voltages.

4.2. Reducing transmission losses

To see the performance of the proposed approach concerning the transmission power losses reduction, another test is performed, adding a new term to the cost function (8). The optimization aims, for each iteration, to minimize total losses at all branches for the same operational conditions as the previous test.

The active power loss between two nodes i and j can be modeled as follows:

$$P_{Lij} = G_{ij} (|V_i|^2 + |V_j|^2 - 2|V_i V_j| \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j)) \quad (8)$$

Where V_i and V_j are the voltages at nodes i and j , respectively; θ_i and θ_j are the voltage phase angles at nodes i and j , respectively; and G_{ij} is the line conductance.

The difference in voltage phase angles between buses initiates a active power flow, while the difference in voltage magnitude initiates reactive power flow. The amount of transported active and reactive powers are formulated in (9).

$$P = \frac{V_i V_j}{X_{ij}} \sin(\delta_{ij}) \quad (9.a)$$

$$Q = \frac{V_i V_j \cos(\delta_{ij}) - V_j^2}{X_{ij}} \quad (9.b)$$

Where X_{ij} is the line reactance; δ_{ij} is the difference in voltage phase angles.

The new objective function expression in this case is formulated in (10).

$$J = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{NB} (1 - V_i)^2}{NB} + K \sum_{j=1}^{NL} PL_j \quad (10)$$

Where PL_j is the power loss of the line j ; NL is the number of lines in the network; K is a weighting factor.

Active power flow through the network lines is usually obtainable after solving an optimal load flow problem, which aims to deal with economic penalties [24–26], while reactive power flow is an undesired consequence associated with connected low power-factor loads. The inductive nature of transmission lines can also initiate reactive power flows. Consequently, power losses through lines as well as voltage degradations at load nodes, especially heavily charged ones, are targeted. This problem can usually be solved, either totally or partially, by adding FACTS devised as reactive power support to the weak buses.

5. Results and discussion

In this section, the proposed method is implemented and simulated using MATLAB platform version (8.3.0.532) on Intel C(TM)2 Duo CPU T6670 @2.20 GHz 2.20 GHz. Five 20 MW PV plants are connected to different locations mentioned previously in a 30-bus IEEE test grid. Technically, a 20 MW PV power plant can be characterized as the one installed at the region of Ain El-Bell, Djelfa (Algeria) (see Table 1), which is connected to a 60 KV transmission line. For simplification reasons, PV plants are modeled as P-Q loads consuming negative active powers and negative/positive reactive powers according to capacitive/inductive behavior of the PV inverters. The active power generation and demand (P_g and P_d), as well as reactive power generation and demand (Q_g and Q_d) at each bus, are listed in Table A1 (Appendices). The characteristics of each branch (transmission line) in the network are listed in Table A2 (Appendices). The MATPOWER model is chosen to perform the simulation, which is a package of MATLAB m-files for solving load power flow and optimal load power flow problems developed by Ray D. Zimmerman et al. [27]; it adopts the resolution of nonlinear equations using Newton-Raphson method. At each load bus, active power demand are assumed to be varying over time according to the curve presented in Fig. 8; this curve, with two peaks, simulates the power demand corresponding to the operation of the heat pumps in winter scenario in residential buildings [28]. For simplicity, in this article we assume that the reactive power demand follows the same curve as the active power with the nominal values listed in Table A1 for each bus.

Fig. 9. Suggested active power profile for each PV plant connected to buses: 6, 8, 11, 19 and 26 from top to bottom.

Fig. 10. Hourly voltage evolution at every load bus with only PV active power feeding.

Table 2
PSO optimization parameters.

Parameter	Value
Maximum iterations	100
Swarm size	80
Number of variables	5
Self-confidence parameter	0.8
Swarm-confidence parameter	1
Inertia weight	0.9
Tolerance	10^{-2}

Table 3
DE optimization parameters.

Parameter	Value
Maximum iterations	200
Population size	90
Number of variables	5
Scaling factor	0.75
Crossover rate	0.75

5.1. Conventional operating of PV power plant

First, a conventional method is presented, in which the totality of available active power for each PV plant is fed to the grid without reactive power exchange. Different power profiles are applied that depend on weather conditions in terms of insolation and temperature of the plant geolocation (Fig. 9). A simulation is performed for the one-day scenario, the voltage evolution for all load buses using the conventional method is displayed in Fig. 10.

5.2. Proposed control

Below, the proposed PV-STATCOM control method is performed and evaluated for the same functioning conditions as chosen for the conventional method. The reactive power amount to be exchanged for each PV plant at every hour is obtained through an optimization process that uses PSO and DE separately. According to the location in the network and the reactive power capability of each PV plant, the optimizer builds up an hourly profile of optimal reactive power exchange for each plant. The main optimization parameters for PSO and DE are listed in Tables 2

Fig. 11. Hourly voltage evolution at every load bus with PSO-optimized reactive power management.

Fig. 12. Hourly voltage evolution at every load bus with DE-optimized reactive power management.

and 3, respectively: the right parameters are reached using a “trial-and-error” method. For example, the number of iteration for both techniques is not too large to avoid high computing times without attaining the optimum point, and not too small to avoid stopping the optimization process before the tolerance criteria is met. In addition, the swarm size for PSO and the population size for DE are also tricky parameters: high values will extend the computing time before reaching the optimum point, while overly small values are not efficient for finding the global optimum. The evolution of load buses voltage using both techniques is displayed in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12. The hourly optimal reactive exchange, using both techniques, is shown in Fig. B1 and Fig. B2 (Appendices). Both optimization techniques give the same optimal profiles due to the same targeted objective.

Discussion

In the conventional method, the voltage level at each load bus depends on the power flux running through this bus and on the localization regarding to nearby generator buses. Because of the nature of the studied daily power demand, the voltage decreases heavily around 12:00 and 19:00, as displayed in Fig. 10; these two points correspond to the peaks in power consumption related to the instantaneous operation of heat pumps in the winter scenario installed in residential buildings. The voltage in this case exceeds the minimum allowed limit (0.95p.u.). Even with the considerable PV power, fed around 12:00, the load buses are still affected by the high power demands. Due to the nature of the high and medium-voltage lines, which are more inductive than the low-voltage lines, the circulation of reactive powers may, in this case, have a significant effect, which explains the reasoning behind the proposed management method: regarding to the location in the grid of each PV plant, PSO and DE can optimally manage the remaining reactive power reserves to improve the voltage globally at all load buses. For a penetration rate of less than 25 percent, this optimized coordination between PV plants can return the voltage at all load nodes to the acceptable

margin $[-0.5 \text{ p.u.} + 0.5 \text{ p.u.}]$. The simulation shows a mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.0085 p.u. and 0.0075 p.u. using DE and PSO, respectively, instead of 0.0237 p.u. using conventional method, which means an improvement of more than 64 percent and 68 percent, respectively.

On the other hand, when adding the transmission losses to the cost function, the optimization this time aims to optimally manage the reactive power circulations in the grid so the totality of transmission losses is reduced. To accomplish this task, PV voltages in coordination, their PCC voltages in order to initiate reactive power flows in the grid opposite to the unnecessary running currents in different branches. Table C1 (Appendices) gathers simulation tests performed in this context. First, active and reactive power losses are evaluated as a test reference when no PV plant is connected. Then, the same quantities are listed when PV plants are connected and driven in a conventional way (feeding active power only). Substantial reductions are attained with 10.22percent and 9.73percent in active and reactive losses reduction, respectively; this is explained by the fact that, with optimal location of PV plants, it is possible to modify the active power flux in some branches so they can compensate losses and sustain weak buses. PSO-based optimization significantly reduces the total transmission losses since it adjusts optimally the voltage at different nodes regarding to their relative positions. The simulation has given 23.51 percent and 24.11 percent as improvements in active and reactive losses reduction, respectively.

The fact that the required data should be collected and transmitted securely and in real-time to a cloud-based database makes this management policy a suitable application for IoT. In this context, this data transfer needs internet-based protocol, such as Open Platform Communications United Architecture (OPC UA) or Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT), or simply LTE mobile networking. The raw data is to be stored initially in a scalable time series database, which is called typically “data lake”. This later forms the basis for real-time visualization via web-based dashboards, for some user applications’ backend. It can also be used as a data backup (long-term storage). Optionally, another database can be used, which is the place for only processed,

cleaned and structured data; this type of database is called a “warehouse database” (not presented in Fig. 5). Warehouse databases can be the backend basis for specific user applications like reporting service (weather trends, plants performance, grid status, etc.). The optimization algorithms, which should also be hosted in the cloud to benefit from better hardware resources, will basically rely on time series databases since updated data are consciously needed. The optimization outcomes can be ideally stored in the warehouse database for reporting, and then sent back, with the same wireless communication protocol, to the PV plants. In this context, each reactive power setpoint is sent to the relevant PV inverter to drive it for the next control horizon. To make it technically feasible, the PV inverters should be associated with a higher-level hardware that can serve as a bridge between the cloud and the inverter control system. This hardware, which is ideally an industrial PC, is able to handle the different high-level communication protocol with the cloud (OPC UA, MQTT, etc.) and at the same time able to deal with the classical protocols used in automation like Modbus, which are adopted widely by many PV inverter manufacturers.

6. Conclusion

This article investigates and simulates a new management algorithm for optimal real-time coordinated operation of PV plants connected to a transmission grid. The method consists of driving PV plants as PV-STATCOM in order to enhance the voltage regulation at load nodes when heavy load power demands take place like operating heat pumps simultaneously in multiple households in a winter day scenario. Additionally, the proposed management can reduce significantly the total transmission losses in the entire grid without adding any additional FACT devices. To accomplish this task, the plants exchange, in coordination, the reactive power with the transmission grid regarding to their locations and their dynamic reactive power capabilities. This coordination is translated to an optimization problem for each operational point. This article suggests the IoT hardware architecture, which makes it possible the implementation of such management strategy. Due to the enlarged distances between PV plants and the edge computer that carries out the optimization task, wireless communication is required, either via IP-based protocols or 3G/LTE. The simulation is performed on MATPWOER model for 30-bus IEEE test grid. Very competitive results are obtained with penetration rate of renewable power of less than 25percent.

The proposed approach is to be improved in the perspective works by adding new terms to the optimization cost function like the voltage stability index. This may improve the voltage dynamic stability in the entire network preventing voltage collapses in the weakest buses.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Test grid parameters

Tables A1 and Table A2.

Table A1
IEEE 30-bus grid rated powers at each bus.

bus_i	Pd (MW)	Qd (MVar)	Pg (MW)	Qg (MVar)
1	0	0	23.54	0
2	21.7	12.7	60.97	0
3	2.4	1.2	0	0
4	7.6	1.6	0	0
5	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0
7	22.8	10.9	0	0
8	30	30	0	0
9	0	0	0	0
10	5.8	2	0	0
11	0	0	0	0
12	11.2	7.5	0	0
13	0	0	37	0
14	6.2	1.6	0	0
15	8.2	2.5	0	0
16	3.5	1.8	0	0
17	9	5.8	0	0
18	3.2	0.9	0	0
19	9.5	3.4	0	0
20	2.2	0.7	0	0
21	17.5	11.2	0	0
22	0	0	21.59	0
23	3.2	1.6	19.2	0
24	8.7	6.7	0	0
25	0	0	0	0
26	3.5	2.3	0	0
27	0	0	26.91	0
28	0	0	0	0
29	2.4	0.9	0	0
30	10.6	1.9	0	0

Table A2
IEEE 30-bus branches parameters.

From bus	To bus	R (p.u.)	X (p.u.)	B (p.u.)
1	2	0.02	0.06	0.03
1	3	0.05	0.19	0.02
2	4	0.06	0.17	0.02
3	4	0.01	0.04	0
2	5	0.05	0.2	0.02
2	6	0.06	0.18	0.02
4	6	0.01	0.04	0
5	7	0.05	0.12	0.01
6	7	0.03	0.08	0.01
6	8	0.01	0.04	0
6	9	0	0.21	0
6	10	0	0.56	0
9	11	0	0.21	0
9	10	0	0.11	0
4	12	0	0.26	0
12	13	0	0.14	0
12	14	0.12	0.26	0
12	15	0.07	0.13	0
12	16	0.09	0.2	0
14	15	0.22	0.2	0
16	17	0.08	0.19	0
15	18	0.11	0.22	0
18	19	0.06	0.13	0
19	20	0.03	0.07	0
10	20	0.09	0.21	0
10	17	0.03	0.08	0
10	21	0.03	0.07	0
10	22	0.07	0.15	0
21	22	0.01	0.02	0
15	23	0.1	0.2	0
22	24	0.12	0.18	0
23	24	0.13	0.27	0
24	25	0.19	0.33	0
25	26	0.25	0.38	0
25	27	0.11	0.21	0
28	27	0	0.4	0
27	29	0.22	0.42	0
27	30	0.32	0.6	0
29	30	0.24	0.45	0
8	28	0.06	0.2	0.02
6	28	0.02	0.06	0.01

Appendix B. Optimal reactive power profiles

Figs. B1 and B2.

Fig. B1. PSO-based optimal reactive hourly profile for each PV plant with superior and inferior reactive power capability limits (from top to bottom, PV plants connected to buses 6, 8, 11, 19 and 26).

Fig. B2. DE-based optimal reactive hourly profile for each PV plant with superior and inferior reactive power capability limits ((from top to bottom, PV plants connected to buses 6, 8, 11, 19 and 26).

Appendix C. Transmission losses optimization result

Table C1.

Table C1

Power transmission losses in IEEE 30-bus branches accumulated during the 24 h of testing.

From bus	To bus	Without PV power plant		With PV power plant (conventional control)		With PV power plant (proposed control)	
		Active losses (MW)	Reactive losses (MVar)	Active losses (MW)	Reactive losses (MVar)	Active losses (MW)	Reactive losses (MVar)
1	2	13.79	41.38	10.57	31.70	10.06	30.17
1	3	13.91	52.86	11.44	43.46	11.25	42.76
2	4	11.43	32.38	9.89	28.01	8.50	24.08
3	4	2.29	9.14	1.84	7.36	1.84	7.34
2	5	6.12	24.49	5.48	21.91	4.57	18.29
2	6	18.15	54.44	15.50	46.51	13.22	39.65
4	6	3.88	15.51	3.19	12.76	2.77	11.09
5	7	6.44	15.45	5.80	13.91	4.63	11.10
6	7	0.88	2.34	1.06	2.83	1.85	4.93
6	8	5.65	22.62	5.63	22.54	2.80	11.21
6	9	0.00	11.91	0.00	8.41	0.00	6.26
6	10	0.00	10.37	0.00	8.78	0.00	6.76
9	11	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.47	0.00	2.67
9	10	0.00	6.24	0.00	7.80	0.00	6.48
4	12	0.00	8.21	0.00	6.62	0.00	5.52
12	13	0.00	53.24	0.00	53.14	0.00	48.85
12	14	1.66	3.60	1.62	3.52	1.58	3.43
12	15	3.57	6.64	3.36	6.25	3.38	6.27
12	16	2.16	4.80	1.94	4.31	1.94	4.30
14	15	0.14	0.12	0.14	0.12	0.16	0.14
16	17	0.70	1.65	0.59	1.39	0.63	1.49
15	18	3.07	6.14	2.91	5.82	3.04	6.07
18	19	0.59	1.28	0.54	1.17	0.83	1.79
19	20	0.46	1.08	0.49	1.14	0.34	0.80
10	20	2.62	6.11	2.72	6.35	2.02	4.71
10	17	0.60	1.60	0.61	1.62	0.64	1.71
10	21	2.01	4.70	1.92	4.49	0.34	0.79
10	22	2.41	5.16	2.30	4.92	0.56	1.20
21	22	3.27	6.53	3.18	6.35	1.93	3.86
15	23	3.52	7.04	3.50	7.01	2.11	4.22
22	24	2.12	3.17	2.02	3.03	1.63	2.45
23	24	1.72	3.57	1.66	3.45	1.66	3.44
24	25	1.11	1.92	1.00	1.73	0.72	1.25
25	26	1.90	2.89	1.90	2.89	1.31	1.99
25	27	2.29	4.37	2.19	4.18	1.96	3.75
28	27	0.00	10.05	0.00	9.33	0.00	1.55
27	29	3.70	7.06	3.70	7.06	3.70	7.06
27	30	7.04	13.20	7.04	13.20	7.04	13.20
29	30	1.44	2.69	1.44	2.69	1.44	2.69
8	28	1.23	4.10	1.22	4.06	0.41	1.38
6	28	0.25	0.74	0.22	0.67	0.19	0.56
Total loss (MW/MVar)		132.12	470.79	118.61	424.96	101.05	357.26
Reduction in (%)		-	-	10.22	9.73	23.51	24.11

References

- [1] Varma Rajiv K, Graham Sanderson, Walsh Ken. Global PV Incentive Policies and Recommendations for Utilities. In: Proc. 2011 IEEE Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering, Niagara Falls, Canada, May 2011.
- [2] Padiyar KR. FACTS Controllers in Power Transmission and Distribution. New Delhi: New Age International (P) Limited; 2007. p. 4–7.
- [3] The World Bank Database (2014) Electric power transmission and distribution losses (% output). <https://data.worldbank.org/>. Accessed 9 Jun 2018.
- [4] Varma RK, Khadkikar V, Seethapathy R. Nighttime Application of PV Solar Farm as STATCOM to Regulate Grid Voltage. IEEE Trans on Energy Conversion (Letters) Dec. 2009;24(4):983–5.
- [5] Varma Rajiv K, Khadkikar Vinod. Utilization of Solar Farm Inverter as STATCOM, US Provisional Patent application filed 15 Sept. 2009.
- [6] Barbosa P, Rolim L, Watanabe E, Hanitsch R. Control strategy for grid-connected DC-AC converters with load power factor correction. IEE Proc Generation, Transmiss Distribut Sep 1998;145(5):487–91.
- [7] Sung-Hun Ko, Seong-Ryong Lee, Hoon Dehbonei, Nayar CV. A Grid-Connected Photovoltaic System with Direct Coupled Power Quality Control. In: 32nd Annual Conference on IEEE Industrial. Paris, France, 06-10 November 2006.
- [8] Lee Su-Won, Kim Jae-Hyung, Lee Seong-Ryong, Lee Byoung-Kuk, Won Chung-Yuen. A Transformerless Grid-Connected Photovoltaic System with Active and Reactive Power Control. In: IEEE 6th International Power Electronics and Motion Control Conference, Wuhan, China, 17–20 May 2009, pp. 2178–2181.
- [9] Varma Rajiv K, Rangarajan Shriram S, Axente Iurie, Sharma Vinay. Novel application of a PV Solar Plant as STATCOM during Night and Day in a Distribution Utility Network. IEEE PES Power Systems Conference & Expo; Phoenix, Arizona, USA, March 20–23, 2011.
- [10] Varma Rajiv K, Das Byomakesh, Axente Iurie, Vanderheide Tim. Optimal 24-hr Utilization of a PV Solar System as STATCOM (PV-STATCOM) in a Distribution Network. In: Proc. IEEE PES General Meeting; Detroit, USA, July 24, 2011.
- [11] Gupta CP, Srivastava SC, Varma RK. Enhancement of static voltage stability margin with reactive power dispatch using FACTS devices. In: 13th PSCC in Trondheim, June 28 – July 2, 1999.
- [12] Rao P, Crow ML, Yang Z. STATCOM Control for Power System Voltage Control Applications. IEEE Trans. Power Delivery, October 2000:1311–7.
- [13] Liu JY, Song YH, Metha P. Strategies for Handling UPFC Constraints in Steady-State Power Flow and Voltage Control. IEEE Trans. Power System, May 2000: 566–71.
- [14] Chen YL. Weak bus oriented reactive power planning for system security. Generati, Transmiss Distribut, IEE Proc 1996;143:541–5.
- [15] Ajarapar V, Christy C. The continuation power flow: a tool for steady state voltage stability analysis. IEEE Trans Power Syst 1992;7(1):416–23.
- [16] Musirin, TKA Rahman. Novel Fast Voltage Stability Index (FVSI) for Voltage Stability Analysis in Power Transmission System. In: Student Conference on Research and Development Proceedings. Shah Alam, Malaysia. 2002.
- [17] Mudlapur Arjun, Raju A, Rao Uma. Evaluation of different PWM techniques for two level inverter in grid connected WECS. In: 2013 International Conference on

- Advances in Computing, Communications and Informatics (ICACCI), 22–25 Aug. 2013.
- [18] Viswanath SK, Yuen C, Tushar W, Li W-T, Wen C-K, Hu K, et al. System design of the internet of things for residential smart grid. *IEEE Wirel Commun* 2016;23:90–8.
- [19] Spall James C. Stochastic Optimization. In: Gentle J., Härdle W, Mori Y (Eds.), *Handbook of Computational Statistics: Concepts and Methods* (2nd ed.), Springer–Verlag, Heidelberg, Chapter 7, pp. 173–201.
- [20] Rahman I, Vasant PM, Singh BSM, Abdullah-Al-Wadud M. On the performance of accelerated particle swarm optimization for charging plug-in hybrid electric vehicles. *Alexan Eng J* 2016;55(1):419–26.
- [21] Rout UK, Sahu RK, Panda S, Sahu Rabindra Kumar, Panda Sidhartha. Design and analysis of differential evolution algorithm based automatic generation control for interconnected power system". *Ain Shams Eng J* 2013;4(3):409–21.
- [22] Kennedy J, Eberhart R. Particle Swarm Optimization. In: *Proceedings of the 1995 IEEE International Conference on Neural Networks* (Perth, Australia): IEEE Service Center, Piscataway, NJ, IV; 1995. p 1942–1948.
- [23] Storn R, Price K. Differential evolution a simple and efficient adaptive scheme for global optimization over continuous spaces. Technical Report TR-95-012, ICSI; March 1995.
- [24] Huneault M, Galiana FD. A survey of the optimal power flow literature. *IEEE Trans Power Systems* May 1991;6(2):762–70.
- [25] Bakistzis AG, Biskas PN, Zoumas CE, Petridis V. Optimal power flow by enhanced genetic algorithm. *IEEE Trans Power Systems* May 2002;17(2):229–36.
- [26] Roa-Sepulveda CA, Pavez-Lazo BJ. A solution to the optimal power flow using simulated annealing. *Electr Power Energy Syst (Elsevier)* 2003;25(1):47–57.
- [27] Zimmerman RD, Murillo-Sánchez CE. *MATPOWER – A MATLAB Power System Simulation Package, User's Manual*. Ithaca, NY: School of Electrical Engineering, Cornell University; September 2007.
- [28] Love Jenny, Smith Andrew ZP, Watson Stephen, Oikonomou Eleni, Summerfield Alex, Gleeson Colin, Biddulph Phillip, Fong Chiu Lai, Wingfield Jez, Martin Chris, Stone Andy, Lowe Robert. The addition of heat pump electricity load profiles to GB electricity demand: Evidence from a heat pump field trial. *Appl Energy*, 2017;204: 332–342.